

Assessment of Genotoxicity in Mammary Tissue by Spectroscopy and Kinetic Modelling

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ABSTRACT

Lithium carbonate (Li_2CO_3) and lead acetate (Pb_2COOH) belong to the female reproductive toxicants that cause infertility through the interference with development of growing follicles in the ovarian tissue. Doxorubicin (Dox) and cyclophosphamide (CPA) are considered as the most effective chemotherapeutic drugs which are associated with the greatest risk of female infertility. Furthermore, whole body gamma irradiation for therapeutic purpose by mean of radiotherapy affected female reproductive organ through destruction of the small and antral follicles. The present study aimed to reveal the deleterious effect of all of these (toxic) substances factors on the cellular macromolecules which separated and identified electrophoretically in the ovarian tissue. During the present study, the toxic factors exhibited qualitative abnormalities represented by disappearance of normal bands and appearance of one or more of abnormal bands. Otherwise, the alterations may occur at the quantitative level through remaining the normal bands but with changing the band quantity. The similarity index (SI) is only correlated to the qualitative alterations. In the electrophoretic protein pattern, the lowest SI value (0.52) was recorded with CPA-treated group and the highest SI value (0.91) noticed with Pb-treated group. In the electrophoretic lipoprotein pattern, there were severe alterations. It was observed that all the bands in the Dox-treated and CPA-treated groups were not matched with all bands of the other groups. In catalase (CAT) pattern, The Pb-treated group is completely identical to control group in number and arrangement of the bands (SI value 1.0). The lowest SI value (0.57) was observed with CPA-treated and Irradiated groups. In peroxidase (POX) pattern, the lowest SI value (0.22) was observed with CPA-treated group and the highest value (0.86) was recorded with Irradiated group. In esterase (EST) pattern, the lowest SI value (0.29) was recorded with the Pb-treated group and the highest SI value (0.80) was noticed with the Li_2CO_3 -treated group. In addition, there was complete similarity between the Dox-treated and Irradiated groups and between CCl_4 -treated and CPA-treated groups. It was postulated that the 3D model of the prolactin receptor specific protein (PRAP) which was built using homology modeling showed that PRAP has large amount of loops. It is expected to be very flexible protein and less stable.

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INTRODUCTION

Environmental factors exert deleterious effects by enhancing the oxidative stress directly or indirectly through generation of reactive oxygen species (ROS) in both unstressed and stressed cells^{1,2}. Rates of production and destruction of ROS were well balanced under normal conditions. However, under stress conditions, the oxidative stress stimulated due to the misbalance through which rate of ROS generation is more rapid than scavenging and detoxifying³. It was demonstrated that the exposure to

environmental stressors caused alterations in the relative compositions of the antioxidant enzymes^{4,5}. Catalase (CAT) and peroxidase (POX) are the most efficient antioxidant enzymes due to their critical role **Author for Correspondence: wmkamel83@hotmail.com* against oxidative stress induced by environmental factors⁶. The normal cells have a variety of defense mechanisms that ameliorate efficiency of the antioxidant enzymes to prevent intracellular damage occurred as a result of ROS attack⁷. The free radicals cause severe alterations in the intracellular macromolecules such as proteins, lipids and

DNA. Proteins are responsible for all biological functions occurred inside the cells. The alterations in the native protein pattern are considered as an important part of physiological response to toxic environmental factors⁸. Modified proteins may be removed by normal cellular turnover, but DNA damage requires specific repair mechanisms. When the genomic DNA is the target of oxidation reaction, it can lead to various mutagenic effects represented by rearrangements and transcriptional errors that stimulate altering expression of different genes⁹. Lithium carbonate (Li_2CO_3) has been used in medicine as an effective drug for curing bipolar disorders, psychiatric and neurological diseases^{10,11} as well as an adjuvant substance in therapy of thyroid disorders¹². It was documented that lithium affected ovary of the adult rats through decline ovarian steroidogenic enzymes and hence lowering the folliculogenesis process. Two weeks of lithium treatment was sufficient to induce toxicity of the female reproductive organs^{13,14}. It was reported that lead acetate (Pb_2COOH) belongs to the reproductive toxicants which cause female infertility through the interference with development of growing follicles in the ovary¹⁵. Although alkylating chemotherapeutic drugs and irradiation are used in treating various cancerous diseases through induction of DNA damage in cancer cells, these treatments have undesired detrimental side effects on the reproductive system¹⁶. Doxorubicin (Dox) and cyclophosphamide (CPA) belong to numerous chemotherapeutic drugs¹⁷. Meirou *et al.*¹⁸ suggested that the mature follicles are the most sensitive target to these chemotherapeutic drugs. Dox is an anthracycline antibiotic used as a potent antineoplastic agent to treat hematological and solid tumours^{19,20}. It was postulated that Dox affected the ovaries which served as a tool for tracking down the whole organ pattern of the Dox gonadotoxic effect. For this reason, Ben-Aharon *et al.*²¹ recommended that further studies needed in the future to shield the ovaries from chemotherapy peril. It was documented that CPA is one of the most effective alkylating agents which are associated with the greatest risk of female infertility²². It targeted primordial and primary follicles. It caused destruction of primordial follicles after one week of treatment by enhancing apoptosis in ovarian follicles. Although the active metabolites of CPA are detoxified by conjugation with glutathione (GSH), the GSH depletion does not seem to be the mechanism by which CPA causes follicular apoptosis²³. In addition, according to *in vivo* studies which performed in rats and mice, it was found that the whole body gamma radiation exposure by mean of radiotherapy destroys small follicles as well as antral follicles²⁴. Prolactin (PRL) is composed of polypeptide hormone and produced primarily in the anterior lobe of pituitary gland²⁵. It plays a vital role in promoting follicular development and its effects are mediated by the prolactin receptor (PRLR)^{26,27}. Expression

of the gene which is responsible for synthesis of PRLR increases during the ovarian development. The PRLR affects the follicular development and maturation²⁸. The PRLR protein is expressed in oocytes and prenatal follicles to increase rate of the oocyte maturation and regulate the reproduction process^{29,30}. According to the crystal structure of PRLR, the computer modeling and simulation showed that there are minor changes in the tertiary structure of the extracellular subdomain 1 upon disruption of disulfide bond which propagated to the quaternary structure of the homodimer. These changes explain a structural basis for lack of inhibitory function of PRLR³¹. The present study aimed to investigate the deleterious effect of various toxic factors on the native electrophoretic protein, lipoprotein and isozymes in the ovarian tissue of rats. This was in association with the 3D models of the PRLR which was built using homology modeling to give a first insight about the structural characteristics of the activated regions in it.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Materials: Chemicals and Reagents

Acrylamide, Bis-acrylamide, Ammonium persulfate (APS), N,N,N,N-Tetramethylethylenediamine (TEMED), Coomassie Brilliant Blue G-250 (CBBR-250) and Sudan Black B (SBB) were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich. Cyclophosphamide (CPA), Doxorubicin (Dox), Lead Acetate Trihydrate, Carbon Tetrachloride (CCl_4), Lithium Carbonate (Li_2CO_3) and Benzidine were procured from Sigma Chemicals Company (London, UK). The chemicals used for in-gel esterase staining including α - and β naphthylacetate, Fast Blue RR were purchased from Qualigens Fine Chemicals, India. All other chemicals and reagents used were of analytical grade and of highest purity.

Animals and Treatments

Seventy adult female rats (weighing between 150-170 gm per one) were housed in the animal house laboratory of national research centre. Each group contains 10 rats. All the animals kept under normal environmental and nutritional conditions at $25 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$. All the experimental procedures were carried out according to the ethical protocol which followed the ethical guidelines and approved by the institutional animal care of National Research Centre, Dokki, Giza, Egypt.

Experimental Design

The rats were randomly divided into 7 groups. Group I (Control group): Rats were fed with normal diet as

PTSX-----PQTQG----LAKD-----AWEIPRESL

PT + PQ+ GL + AE + S

PTRRTFLDPQSCGDLQAVHLFAKELDAKSV

Figure 1: An alignment between two sequences. Conserved amino acids are aligned and insertions are marked with dashes.

Figure 2: Geometry of a simple chain molecule, illustrating the definition of interatomic distance r_{23} , bend angle θ_{234} , and torsion angle Φ_{1234} .

ad libitum and received distilled water for 60 days. Group II (Pb-treated group): Rats received lead acetate at concentration of 30 mg/kg body weight orally by gavage tube for 60 days by gavage tube³². Group III (Li_2CO_3 treated group): Rats were treated with lithium carbonate solution interperitoneally (i.p.) at three dosages of 60,120

And

Figure 3: (a) Electrophoretic protein pattern showing toxic effect of Pb_2COOH , Li_2CO_3 , Dox, CCl_4 , CPA and irradiation on protein pattern in ovarian tissue of female rats, (b) Dendrogram showing the similarity and relationship among Pb-treated, Li_2CO_3 -treated, Dox-treated, CCl_4 -treated, CPA-treated and Irradiated groups in female rats as compared to control.

Figure 4: (a) Electrophoretic lipoprotein pattern showing toxic effect of Pb_2COOH , Li_2CO_3 , Dox, CCl_4 , CPA and irradiation on protein pattern in ovarian tissue of female rats, (b) Dendrogram showing the similarity and relationship among Pb-treated, Li_2CO_3 -treated, Dox-treated, CCl_4 -treated, CPA-treated and Irradiated groups in female rats as compared to control.

Figure 5: (a) Electrophoretic CAT pattern showing toxic effect of Pb₂COOH, Li₂CO₃, Dox, CCl₄, CPA and irradiation on protein pattern in ovarian tissue of female rats, (b) Dendrogram showing the similarity and relationship among Pb-treated, Li₂CO₃-treated, Dox-treated, CCl₄-treated, CPA-treated and Irradiated groups in female rats as compared to control.

mg/kg B.W for 21 days³³. Group IV (Dox-treated group): Rats received Dox at dose level of 25mg/kg b.wt for three times per week for two weeks³⁴. Group V (CCl₄-treated group): Rats were injected with CCl₄ i.p. at the dose 0.5 ml/kg b.w. (50 % CCl₄ in olive oil) twice a week for 28 days³⁵. Group

VI (CPA-treated group): Rats received CPA i.p. at 40 mg/kg b.w. twice a week for 15 days³⁶. Group VII (Irradiated group): Rats were exposed to single dose of 7 Gy delivered at the dose rate of 1.167 Rad / Sec. at Middle Eastern Regional Radioisotope Centre for the Arab Countries, Dokki, Egypt using Cobalt 60 (Co⁶⁰)³⁷. *Extraction of ovarian tissue homogenates* All the animals were anaesthetized and killed by decapitation. Ovaries were quickly dissected and cleaned carefully from superficial fatty layer and then washed in ice-cold saline. As reported by **Elshawi et al.**³⁸, the ovaries were frozen rapidly with liquid nitrogen then homogenized in 1 ml water-soluble

extraction buffer. The homogenates vortexed for 15 seconds then centrifuged at 10,000 rpm at 4°C for 15 min. The clear supernatants containing water-soluble proteins were transferred to new eppendorf tubes and kept at deep-freeze until the electrophoretic patterns. *Determination of protein concentration* All samples of each group were pooled together and used as one sample. Protein concentration was estimated in the ovarian tissue homogenates according to method described by Bradford³⁹ using bovine serum albumin as standard. The protein concentration in each well should be in the range between 60-80 µg protein. Equal quantities of protein were loaded in all wells. *Electrophoretic protein and lipoprotein patterns*

To determine the relative mobility (R_m), molecular weight (Mwt) and band percent (Ba %) of the isolated proteins and lipoproteins, the native 10 % polyacrylamide gel electrophoresis of samples was carried out according to method suggested by Laemmli⁴⁰ using Mini-gel

Figure 6: (a) Electrophoretic POX pattern showing toxic effect of Pb_2COOH , Li_2CO_3 , Dox, CCl_4 , CPA and irradiation on protein pattern in ovarian tissue of female rats, (b) Dendrogram showing the similarity and relationship among Pb-treated, Li_2CO_3 -treated, Dox-treated, CCl_4 -treated, CPA-treated and Irradiated groups in female rats as compared to control.

Figure 7: (a) Electrophoretic EST pattern showing toxic effect of Pb_2COOH , Li_2CO_3 , Dox, CCl_4 , CPA and irradiation on protein pattern in ovarian tissue of female rats, (b) Dendrogram showing the similarity and relationship among Pb-treated, Li_2CO_3 -treated, Dox-treated, CCl_4 -treated, CPA-treated and Irradiated groups in female rats as compared to control.

Figure 8: Sequence alignments of PRAP and homologs sequences obtained by pairwise algorithm. Residues are colored based on their properties.

electrophoresis (BioRad, USA), with the modification that samples, gels and running buffers were lacking SDS. The gels contained Acrylamide/Bis (30% T, 2.67% C) (Acrylamide: bis-acrylamide = 29.2:0.8) and 10% glycerol. The gel was run in buffer containing Tris (24 mM) and glycine (194 mM) at room temperature. Five microletre of the marker loaded in the first well with the samples each run. After completing the electrophoretic run, protein bands were visualized by staining with Coomassie Brilliant Blue G-250 and destained overnight with 7%

(v/v) glacial acetic acid after documentation⁴¹. The molecular weight of the separated proteins was estimated in comparison to marker of standard molecular weights with regularly spaced bands ranging from 6.458 to 195.755 KDa. The native gels were also stained for lipid with Sudan Black B (SBB)⁴².

Electrophoretic localization of in-gel enzyme activity

The non-denaturing gel was stained for electrophoretic POX pattern using benzidine stain prepared according to method described by Rescigno *et al.*⁴³. It was stained for electrophoretic CAT pattern according to method of

Siciliano and Shaw⁴⁴. The native gel was processed for localization of in-gel EST

activity according to method suggested by Ahmad *et al.*⁴⁵ who postulated that the gel was incubated in reaction mixture containing α , β -naphthyl acetate (5.58×10^{-3} mM, pH 7.5) as substrates along with dye coupler Fast Blue RR at 25°C in dark. After developing the colored bands of EST activity, the reaction was stopped by fixing the gels in 7% glacial acetic acid for 30 min, followed by preserving the gel in 5% acetic acid prepared in 10% methanol.

Data analysis

All the native polyacrylamide gel plates were analyzed using Phoretix 1D pro software (Version 12.3). The similarity index (SI) was calculated according to equation suggested by Nei and Li⁴⁶ to compare all treated groups to control group.

Computational Methods Comparative Protein Modeling

Comparative protein modeling uses previously solved structures as starting points, or templates. This is effective because it appears that although the number of actual proteins is vast, there is a limited set of tertiary structural motifs to which most proteins belong. It has been suggested that there are only around 2000 distinct protein folds in nature, though there are many millions of different proteins. Sequence-based methods for identifying protein homology compare sequences to find similarities that are unlikely to occur by chance. Essentially all methods employ some sort of scheme to judge amino acid substitutions, insertions and deletions. Based on the scoring scheme a query sequence is aligned to another sequence or to a profile that represents a set of sequences. In an alignment equivalent amino acids are set side-by-side so that insertions and deletions become apparent as shown in Fig. 1. The score of the sequence, which is used to detect homology, is directly related to the alignment. Profileprofile sequence-based homology detection was used. Sequences can be scored globally or locally. In the (3.69)

former case, the alignment is over the entire length of the sequences. From a biological point of view this is not always desired because related proteins may not have recognizable homology along their entire length. Proteins may for example share only one out of several domains. Local scoring aligns subsequences only and can be better for finding local similarities. It is also possible to align a global domain model locally to a sequence, (global/local scoring) or to align part of a domain model locally to a sequence (local/local scoring). Profile-profile methods are more sensitive⁴⁷ than both profile based and pair-wise methods^{48,49}.

Molecular Dynamics Simulations

Conceptually, molecular dynamics simulations are quite simple. In these simulations, we follow the trajectories of N particles interacting via a many-body potential $U(r_1, r_2, \dots, r_N)$ using Newton's equation of motion⁵⁰: $m_i \frac{d^2 r_i}{dt^2} = -\nabla_i U(r_1, \dots, r_N)$; $i = 1, \dots, N$

Where m_i and r_i denote the mass and position of the particle, and the force on it is given by the gradient of the potential U . Unlike in Brownian dynamics simulations, in which only the ions are simulated explicitly, in molecular dynamics all the atoms (ions, water, protein and lipid) can be included. At every time step, the potential function is recalculated using the new positions of the particles to determine their positions a short time later, and this process is iterated for a large number of steps until a statistically satisfactory data set is generated. The success of molecular dynamics simulations in capturing the dynamics of the real system hinges critically on how accurately the potential functions or force fields are selected. In the past two decades, numerous studies have been carried out to develop force fields for biomolecular applications, and these are incorporated into several user-friendly computer programs for simulation of biomolecular systems^{51,52}. In these programs, the non-bonded interactions between atoms are represented by Coulomb and Lennard-Jones

respectively.

Table 2: Electrophoretic pattern in the ovarian tissue showing the toxic effect on lipoprotein pattern in Pb-treated, Li₂CO₃-treated, Dox-treated, CCl₄-treated, CPA-treated and Irradiated groups of female rats.

Control		Toxic substances											
		Pb-treated		Li ₂ CO ₃ treated		Dox-treated		CCl ₄ -treated		CPA-treated		Irradiated	
Rm	Ba %	Rm	Ba %	Rm	Ba %	Rm	Ba %	Rm	Ba %	Rm	Ba %	Rm	Ba %
0.04	70.57	0.04	35.78	0.05	11.37	0.11	—	0.11	100	0.04	11.09	0.04	7.34
0.46	16.66	0.22	64.22	0.23	88.63	—	—	—	—	0.1	33.5	0.08	9.3
0.59	12.77	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	0.25	55.41	0.14	83.37

Rm: Relative mobility, Ba %: Band Percent. f the bands in each lane is not correlated Arrangement o with the bands in the other lanes.

Table 3: Electrophoretic pattern in the ovarian tissue showing the toxic effect on CAT pattern in Pb-treated, Li₂CO₃-treated, Dox-treated, CCl₄-treated, CPA-treated and Irradiated groups of female rats.

Control		Toxic substances											
		Pb-treated		Li ₂ CO ₃ treated		Dox-treated		CCl ₄ -treated		CPA-treated		Irradiated	
Rm	Ba %	Rm	Ba %	Rm	Ba %	Rm	Ba %	Rm	Ba %	Rm	Ba %	Rm	Ba %
0.06	25.63	0.05	26.05	0.06	22.8	0.05	23.26	0.06	29.83	0.05	37.29	0.06	17.46
0.26	20.76	0.26	21.54	0.26	20.25	0.25	20.14	0.24	44.42	0.18	36.69	0.19	15.78
0.48	34.62	0.48	32.89	0.34	19.43	0.32	26.64	0.96	25.75	0.96	26.02	0.97	66.77
0.98	18.99	0.97	19.52	0.42	20.46	0.97	29.96	—	—	—	—	—	—
—	—	—	—	0.97	17.06	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—

Rm: Relative Mobility, Ba %: Band Percent.

In each lane, arrangement of the bands is not correlated to arrangement of the bands in the other lanes.

Table 4: Electrophoretic pattern in the ovarian tissue showing the toxic effect on POX pattern in Pb-treated, Li₂CO₃treated, Dox-treated, CCl₄-treated, CPA-treated and Irradiated groups of female rats.

Rm: Relative Mobility, Ba %: Band Percent.

Arrangement of the bands at each lane is not correlated with the bands in the other lanes.

it was noticed that the lowest SI value (0.52) was recorded with CPA-treated group and the highest SI value (0.91) was recorded with Pb-treated group (Fig. 3b). In the healthy ovarian tissue, lipoprotein pattern produced 3 bands with Rms 0.04, 0.46 and 0.59 (Ba % 70.57, 16.66 and 12.77) respectively. There were no common bands. The 1st band was considered as common band in all the groups except Dox-treated and CPA-treated groups (Table 2 and Fig. 4a). In the Pb-treated and Li₂CO₃-treated groups, the qualitative and quantitative alterations occurred with the same degree. In Pb-treated group, these disturbances were represented by disappearance of 2 normal bands with appearance of one abnormal band with Rfm0.22 (Ba % 64.22). In addition, the quantitative mutation occurred by decreasing Ba % of the 1st band (Rm 0.04 and Ba % 35.78). In Li₂CO₃-treated group, the abnormal band was appeared with Rm 0.23 (Ba % 88.63) and the quantitative mutation represented by decreasing Ba % of the 1st band (Rm 0.05 and Ba % 11.37). In the Doxtreated and CPA-treated groups, the alteration occurred qualitatively with the same degree by disappearance of the normal bands with appearance of one abnormal band with Rm 0.11 (Ba % 100.00). In the CCl₄-treated and irradiated groups, the alteration occurred quantitatively with the same degree by disappearance of 2 normal bands with appearance of 2 abnormal band with Rms 0.10 and 0.25 (Ba % 33.50 and 55.41) as in CCl₄-treated group and with Rms 0.080 and 0.14 (Ba % 9.30 and 83.37) as in the irradiated group. As illustrated in Fig. 4b, the lowest SI value (0.33) was recorded with CCl₄-treated and Irradiated groups. The

highest SI (0.40) was noticed with Pb-treated and Li₂CO₃-treated groups. Moreover, in the Dox-treated and CPA-treated groups, it was observed that all the bands were not matched with all bands in the other groups. The electrophoretic CAT pattern showed that 4 types of the enzyme were noticed in healthy ovarian tissue with Rms 0.06, 0.26, 0.48 and 0.98 (Ba % values 25.63, 20.76, 34.62 and 18.99) respectively. There were 2 common bands

appeared with Rms 0.06 and 0.98 (Ba % 25.63 and 18.99). As compared to control, no qualitative or quantitative alterations observed in Pb-treated group. In the Li₂CO₃treated group, the qualitative alterations represented by disappearance of one normal type with appearance of 2 abnormal types with Rms 0.34 and 0.42 (Ba % 19.43 and 20.46). In the Dox-treated group, the qualitative mutation was represented by deviation of the 3rd normal type to be appeared with Rm 0.32 (Ba % 26.64). While in the CCl₄treated group, the mutation was represented by disappearance of the 3rd type of the enzyme completely. The electrophoretic alterations were identical in the CPA-treated and Irradiated groups. These alterations were represented by disappearance of the 3rd type with deviation of the 2nd type of the enzyme to be appeared with Rm 0.18 (Ba % 36.69). On the other hand, there was quantitative alterations occurred in Ba % of the 1st and 4th types of the enzyme in both groups (Table 3 and Fig. 5a). As illustrated in the Fig. 5b, the lowest SI value (0.57) was observed with CPA-treated and Irradiated groups. The Pb-treated group was completely identical to control group in number and arrangement of the bands (the highest SI value

1.0). Electrophoretic POX pattern showed that 3 types of this enzyme were produced in control ovarian tissue with Rms 0.32, 0.60 and 0.85 (Ba % values 0.57, 40.48 and 58.95) respectively. There were no common bands. As revealed in Table 4 and illustrated in Fig. 6a, the 3rd type of the enzyme (Rm 0.85 and Ba % 58.95) was considered as common band in all groups except Li₂CO₃-treated and Dox-treated groups. In the Pb-treated group, the qualitative alteration was represented by disappearance of the 1st type. The quantitative mutation was represented by decreasing Ba % of the 2nd type (Rm 0.61 and Ba % 1.66) and increasing Ba % of the 3rd type (Rm 0.84 and Ba % 98.34). The abnormalities occurred in the Li₂CO₃-treated group were represented qualitatively by disappearance of the 1st type with appearance of 2 abnormal bands (Rms 0.38, 0.47, Ba % values 12.66 and 19.88). This was in addition to the quantitative mutation which was represented by decreasing Ba % of the 2nd type (Rm 0.60 and Ba % 1.48). In Dox-treated group, There were alterations were represented qualitatively by appearance of 2 abnormal bands with Rms 0.19 and 0.50 (Ba % 16.36 and 11.61). Also, these alterations were represented quantitatively by increasing Ba % of the 1st type (Rm 0.33 and Ba % 19.22) and decreasing Ba % of the 2nd type (Rm 0.60 and Ba % 0.50). In CCl₄-treated group, the alterations were represented by disappearance of the 1st type with appearance of one abnormal band (Rm 0.48 and Ba % 17.09). Moreover, the 3rd type deviated to be appeared with Rm 0.82 (Ba % 81.93). The quantitative alteration was represented by decreasing Ba % of the 2nd type (Rm 0.59 and Ba % 0.98) and increasing Ba % of the 3rd type (Rm 0.82 and Ba % 81.93). In CPA-treated group, the qualitative mutation was represented by appearance of 3 abnormal bands with Rms 0.14, 0.25 and 0.44 (Ba % values 13.22, 10.53 and 14.82) respectively. This was in association with deviation of the 1st and 3rd types to be appeared with Rms 0.35 and 0.82 (Ba % 10.91 and 49.76). The mutation occurred quantitatively by increasing Ba % of the 1st type (Rm 0.35 and Ba % 10.91) and decreasing Ba % of the 2nd type of the enzyme (Rm 0.59 and Ba % 0.76). In irradiated group, the mutation occurred qualitatively by appearance of one abnormal band (Rm 0.78 and Ba % 33.48) and quantitatively by increasing Ba % of the 1st type (Rm 0.32 and Ba % 38.92) and decreasing Ba % of the 2nd and 3rd types of the enzyme (Rms 0.59, 0.83, Ba % values 0.57 and 27.04). The SI values were ranged between 0.22 – 0.86. The lowest SI value (0.22) was recorded with CPA-treated group and the highest value (0.86) was noticed with irradiated group (Fig. 6b). As recorded in Table 5 and illustrated in Fig. 7a, the electrophoretic EST pattern showed that 3 types of this enzyme produced in healthy ovarian tissue with Rms 0.24, 0.38 and 0.76 (Ba % 54.11, 23.65 and 22.24) respectively.

There were no common bands. The 3rd type was considered as common band in all groups except Pb-treated and CCl₄-treated groups. In the Pb-treated group, the qualitative mutation represented by appearance of one abnormal characteristic band with Rm 0.15 (Ba % 38.65). This was in addition to the quantitative mutation represented by decreasing Ba % of the 1st normal type (Rm 0.24 and Ba % 12.36). Lithium caused mutation represented qualitatively by disappearance of the 2nd normal type and quantitatively by increasing Ba % of the 3rd type of the enzyme (Rm 0.78 and Ba % 55.88). There were no qualitative or quantitative alterations in the Dox-treated group. While in the irradiated group, the alteration occurred quantitatively by decreasing Ba % of the 1st type (Rm 0.26 and Ba % 37.68) and increasing Ba % of the 3rd type of the enzyme (Rm 0.78 and Ba % 45.37). In the CCl₄-treated group, the alterations were represented qualitatively by disappearance of the 3rd normal type with deviation of the 1st type to be appeared with Rm 0.27 (Ba % 73.67). This was in addition to the quantitative mutation occurred by increasing Ba % of the 1st type of the enzyme (Rm 0.27 and Ba % 73.67). While in the CPA-treated group, the alteration was represented by disappearance of the 1st type with increasing Ba % of the 2nd type of the enzyme (Rm 0.39 and Ba % 78.08). The lowest SI value (0.29) was reported with the Pb-treated group and the highest SI value (0.80) was noticed with the Li₂CO₃-treated group. As revealed in the Fig. 7b, there was complete similarity between the Dox-treated and Irradiated groups and between CCl₄-treated and CPA-treated groups. Homology of PRAP was constructed by restraint-based comparative modeling using templates obtained from FASTA and BLAST databases [H. McWilliam H, W. Li, M. Uludag, S. Squizzato, Y. M. Park, N. Buso, A. P. Cowley, R. Lopez, Analysis Tool Web Services from the EMBL-EBI, Nucleic acids research 41 (Web Server issue): W597-600 (2013 Jul) - A. Morgulis, G. Coulouris, Y. Raytselis, T. L. Madden, R. Agarwala, A. A. Schäffer, "Database indexing for production MegaBLAST searches." *Bioinformatics* 15: 1757-1764 (2008)]. Templates were selected according to the similarity with the query sequence (with similarity percent of 21.0±2%). The model was construct using multiple alignment by means of restraint-based comparative modeling, using the X-ray crystallographic structures of Interleukin-6 receptor (PDB ID: 3l5h, and 3l5i), modular Xyn30D from *Paenibacillus barcinonensis* (PDB ID: 4qaw), and tyrosine-protein phosphatase S (PDB: 2fh7) as templates. [Y. Zhang. I-TASSER server for protein 3D structure prediction. *BMC Bioinformatics*, 9:40 (2008) - A. Roy, A. Kucukural, Y. Zhang. I-TASSER: a unified platform for automated protein structure and function prediction.

Nature Protocols, vol 5, 725-738 (2010) - A. Roy, J. Yang, Y. Zhang. COFACTOR: an accurate comparative algorithm for structure-based protein function annotation. Nucleic Acids Research, 40, W471-W477 (2012)]. Pairwise alignment between PRAP and homologs sequences is presented in Fig. 8. It is obvious that the global alignment shows good agreement between the sequences. Using these alignment results, novel model of PRAP protein was constructed and minimized. As illustrated in Fig. 9a, the data show the constructed model where it can be seen that it consists of coil secondary structure. The constructed model was tested by superimposing the receptor domain (residues 1 - 240) with a recently released prolactin receptor complex domain (PDB: 4I18_C) [10.2210/pdb4i18/pdb] where the calculated root mean square (RMS) was only 3.62 Å (see Fig. 9b).

DISCUSSION

Proteins are the most susceptible macromolecules to be oxidized than others. This depends on the relative content of oxidation-sensitive amino acid residues⁵⁴. Polyacrylamide gel electrophoresis was used for separation and identifying of different proteins and isoenzymes. During the present study, this technique was used to show the deleterious effect of various toxic factors on the different intracellular macromolecules inside the ovarian tissue in rats. During the present study, lithium and lead caused alterations in the native protein pattern detected electrophoretically in the ovarian tissue. This may be due to the presence of specific metal-binding sites⁵⁵. The metal-catalysed oxidation is considered as the most common mechanism which is responsible for protein oxidation. During this mechanism, these metal ions bind to metal binding sites within proteins and react with H₂O₂ to generate hydroxyl radicals that attack neighboring amino acid residues^{56,57}. The variations in electrophoretic mobility may be attributed to effect of the free radicals on integrity of the polypeptide chain in the protein molecule. Subsequently, this leads to sulfhydryl-mediated cross linking of the labile amino acids and hence fragmentation of the polypeptide chains⁵⁸. According to results of the current study, it was found that all the toxic factors selected to be under this study caused electrophoretic alterations in the native protein pattern. This may refer to generation of the free radicals which exhibit modifications in the amino acids through their direct reaction with side chains. It was found previously that the amino acids which contain aromatic side chain groups are the most sensitive to the free radicals attack and these amino acids form carbonyl products irreversibly during the oxidation reaction⁵⁹. Lipoproteins carry all types of lipids, but in different

proportions. The density is directly proportional to the protein content and inversely proportional to the lipid content⁶⁰. For this reason, the alterations in the lipoprotein pattern may refer to the changes in the protein portion. The variations in isoenzymes seem to be good markers of the physiological changes in granulosa cells in the ovary⁶¹. During the current experimental study, it was found that all the toxic factors caused disturbances in the electrophoretic isoenzymes. This was in accordance with El-Zayat⁶² who emphasized the changes in the fractional activity of different isoenzymes seemed to be correlated with changes in the rate of protein expression secondary to DNA damage initiated by free radicals. In addition, further studies confirmed that the differences in the electrophoretic isoenzymes may be attributed due to effect of the free radicals which cause oxidation at level of the nucleic acids. This leads to the formation of various molecular lesions including oxidized bases (purines and pyrimidines), abasic sites (apurinic/apyrimidinic sites) and DNA single- and/or double-strand breaks. Guanine is the most DNA base which is susceptible to be oxidized⁶³. Hydroxyl radicals react with pyrimidines (thymine and cytosine) at positions 5 or 6 of the ring producing several lesions⁶⁴. It was found that the follicular fluid microenvironment contains leukocytes, macrophages and cytokines which are considered as sources of ROS⁶⁵. Due to data of the present study, it was found that there were severe alterations in CAT and POX in the ovarian tissue. This might be occurred due to effect of the free radicals generated as a result of the exposure to these toxic factors. These free radicals caused several molecular alterations involving directly in accumulation of genetic changes and depletion of antioxidant enzymes⁶⁶. Moreover, Peltola *et al.* (1994)⁶⁷ reported that the disturbances in electrophoretic CAT isoenzymes in the ovarian tissue might be related to oxidative stress and attack of the free radicals to protein portion of the native enzymes. On the other hand, it is well known that the chemotherapeutic drugs caused depletion of GSH²³. The alterations in the electrophoretic POX pattern may be caused due to depletion in the level of reduced GSH⁶⁸. This leads to elevation of H₂O₂ and hence generation of the free radicals⁶⁹. The oocytes and granulosa cells of secondary follicles are rich in EST enzyme⁷⁰. The alterations in the electrophoretic EST pattern may occur due to expression of various markers of oxidative stress⁷¹. The cellular endocytosis occurred as a result of enhancing expression of the PRLR and stimulating phosphorylation of the PRLR at Ser-349. Moreover, degradation of the cell occurred through reducing PRLR expression⁷². It was demonstrated previously that down-regulation of the receptor occurred under control of the hormones which decrease expression of the genes which are responsible for

synthesis of these receptors and hence reducing the receptors affinity⁷³. Understanding structure of PRAP is vital because it is included in various metabolic reactions as well as interaction with certain hormones and it was found to exist in certain tumor cell reactions [Jan van Agthoven, Chi Zhang, Estelle Tallet, Bertrand Raynal, Sylviane Hoos, Bruno Baron, Patrick England, Vincent Goffin, Isabelle Broutin, Journal of Molecular Biology, 404, 112 – 126 (2013)]. During the current study, it was postulated that PRAP is expected to be very flexible protein and might be less stable as compared to the Dual specificity testis-specific protein kinase 1 which is predominantly expressed in testicular germ cells and may play an important role in spermatogenesis. This may refer to the large amount of loops on it that was resulted from the 3D homology modeling.

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